

Governing Open Data Platforms to Cultivate Innovation Ecosystems: The Case of the Government of Buenos Aires

Short Paper

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Abstract

Open Government Data (OGD) is increasingly an object of research. Whilst referred to as a platform problem, few studies examine the phenomenon using platform concepts. One challenge governments face is to establish thriving OGD ecosystems through appropriate platform governance. The governance of innovating complements on the demand side of platforms, such as services using OGD datasets by entrepreneurs for citizen users, is well studied in platform literature. However, understanding of the supply side and how third parties can be governed to help innovate platform core architecture, such a ministries sourcing quality datasets for OGD platforms, is lacking. In our preliminary study of emergent OGD platforms in Latin America, we construct a model extending concepts of boundary resources from the demand side to the supply side to expand our understanding of platform governance. In addition to contributing to platform governance theories, we improve our understanding of OGD platform ecosystem cultivation.

Keywords: Open government data platforms, e-government in emerging economies, digital entrepreneurship, platform governance, platform innovation, platform architecture, boundary resources, platform ecosystem cultivation

Introduction

Open government data (OGD) platforms are an emergent phenomenon of the past ten years. They have also become a focal object of research due to their potential to bring about innovation and entrepreneurial activity, build better public services, increase transparency and contribute to wider social policy benefits. Earlier analysis has focused on exploratory research concerning how governments open up and publish their data. Researchers have addressed government's motivations and determinants to open up data (Yang and Wu 2016), data quality and the effects of legislation on open data initiatives (Janssen 2011). A growing number of studies have focused on usage or developing ecosystem approaches (Dawes et al. 2016) to include the demand side of open data users, innovators or entrepreneurs. Some recent studies also refer to OGD as "platforms" (Ruijter et al. 2017), but to date there has been little research on the matter from a platform perspective (Danneels et al. 2017). This is certainly the case from the vantage point of innovation platforms and associated ecosystems of third party innovators and entrepreneurs, who capitalize on the datasets of an open data platform to provide services to citizens, as well as of government agencies who supply datasets that fuel the capabilities of these platforms. This is curious when in practice, open data government platforms are frequently used this way, as we see in transportation apps such as Citymapper. We believe that the OGD literature has much to benefit from innovation platform concepts (de Reuver et al. 2016), particularly with respect the cultivation of a rich ecosystem of developers, suppliers and citizen users.

Despite expectations, achieving the economic and social benefits of open government data is seldom straightforward (The Economist 2015). Part of the problem that governments face is the need to cultivate an ecosystem both on what we term the demand side and the supply side of an OGD platform. On the demand side, the platform authority responsible for the OGD platform needs to cultivate an installed base of independent third party entrepreneurs to innovate services, or applications that use open data, as well as citizen users to consume these services. The cultivation of an ecosystem around a multi-sided digital platform consisting of developers and consumers of services has previously been examined as an issue of economic incentives (Parker and Van Alstyne 2005) and governance (Iansiti and Levien 2004). On the supply side, the OGD platform authority needs to cultivate an installed base of government agencies to provide datasets. Simply put, without a meaningful range of quality datasets the OGD platform is unable to resource developers and consumers of open government data. A key issue that the OGD platform authority then faces is the need to attract and manage government agencies to provide quality datasets.

The closest attempt to date at understanding how government agencies grow or cultivate OGD platform ecosystems is provided by Dawes et. al. (2016). Their approach builds a model, which goes some way to describing the relationships between the key stakeholders and the influences on OGD policies and strategies in the planning and design of OGD programs. Whilst this contribution is helpful, it does not investigate OGD as a platform phenomenon. In this paper, we propose to apply platform theory and terminology. This approach provides more precision in terms of how an OGD platform ecosystem is established.

Research into the governance of software based digital platforms for the innovation of services has largely focused on managing the demand side's use of platform functionality for the development of services (Wareham et al. 2014) that have value to users and which grow the platform ecosystem. In this respect, the understanding of how platform authorities govern the demand side through boundary resources (Eaton et al. 2015) has been fruitful. However, the governance problem faced by an OGD platform authority is both different and broader. First, the underlying architectural focus of the platform core (Baldwin and Woodard 2009) is around the provision of data, rather than functionality, to complementors who then innovate services. Second, the platform authority is reliant on obtaining the modules that make up the platform core and that are then opened up to complementors (on the demand side) from external contributors (on the supply side) instead of developing them in-house. Contributors of datasets to an OGD platform are typically government ministries who are independent of the platform authority. The platform authority must then govern the supply side for the provision of quality datasets as well as govern the demand side for the use of datasets in order to build up a healthy platform ecosystem. In this research work in progress, our research question therefore addresses the need to understand: *How does an OGD platform authority govern its supply side to facilitate the cultivation of an innovation platform ecosystem?*

The aim of our research in progress is to generate an initial model which describes how an OGD platform authority is able to govern the supply side of its platform to facilitate the cultivation of a platform ecosystem. In addition, and consistent previous research on two sided platforms (Evans and Schmalensee 2010), we also aim to reveal how governance on the supply side of the model interacts with governance on the demand side in the facilitation of ecosystem cultivation. To address our research question we investigate the evolution of the ecosystem and governance associated with an open government data platform established by the government of the city of Buenos Aires in Argentina. The outcome of our analysis is to extend models of the governance of innovation of platform complements by third parties on the demand side to encompass the governance of third party involvement in the innovation of core platform architecture on the supply side.

The paper is structured as follows. In the next section we conceptualize the innovation of platform architecture and present boundary resources (Ghazawneh and Henfridsson 2013) to theorize governance of platform innovation. We then outline the methodological approach used in our ongoing study. We present our analysis to reveal how the platform was resourced, how this was governed and the underlying factors enabling this. Finally we discuss an initial model that describes our interpretation of how an OGD platform authority governs both its demand and supply side in order to cultivate a platform ecosystem.

Conceptual Foundations for the Research

It is increasingly recognized that there are different categories of platform (Evans and Gawer 2016), of which the most pervasive are 1) transaction platforms and 2) innovation platforms. Transaction platforms

provide the basis for the exchange of digital information between actors, and whose study is typically informed by economic theory (Gawer 2014). Innovation platforms provide the architectural basis for the innovation of digital services, and are typically studied from the perspective of software engineering design (Gawer 2014). We study OGD platforms as innovation platforms as they enable the innovation of data rich services. On this basis, we define innovation platforms as “foundations upon which other firms can build complementary products, services or technologies” (Gawer 2009, p. 54). We focus on a digital innovation platform’s architecture, which is typically modular (Ulrich 1995) and partitioned into a core and periphery (Baldwin and Woodard 2009), as well as the governance of platform innovation (Wareham et al. 2014).

The Architecture of Digital Innovation Platforms and the Role of Coring

The capacity for a platform to support innovation lies partly in the composition of its architecture, and the degree to which that architecture is open. In this way, “a platform architecture partitions a system into stable core components and variable peripheral components” (Baldwin and Woodard 2009, p. 24). The core architectural component contains “accessible innovative capabilities” (Gawer 2014) that can potentially be drawn through “interfaces” to innovate a build platform complements, such as apps and services. Access to underlying modules through interfaces is in turn governed by “design rules” (Baldwin and Clark 2000). The degree to which their interfaces are open or closed (Boudreau 2010) affects the potential of digital innovation platforms to support innovative contributions from third parties. The innovation of platform complements occurs within the peripheral architecture of a platform and is enabled, in part, by the generative potential (Zittrain 2009) of the architecture of the platform core. The generative potential of the platform is derived from the scope of modules which are embedded in the architecture of the platform core, opened up through and made available for the creation of platform complements.

Innovation platforms are characterized by having platform authorities (Boudreau and Hagiu 2009) responsible for managing and evolving the core architecture as well as governing the broader ecosystem of developers. Platform authorities have strategies which enable them to create and maintain successful platforms (Gawer and Cusumano 2008). These include product coring (Gawer and Cusumano 2008) as a strategy to transform a product into a platform. This approach has been further developed in the IS literature as a means to establish and extend new modular capabilities in the platform core architecture when none existed before (Toppenberg et al. 2016). There are a number of coring strategies ranging from platform authorities developing their own resources to them acquiring external resources. An alternative approach, which is not considered in the emergent literature on platform coring strategies (Toppenberg et al. 2016), is for platform authorities to license or source capabilities from third parties and integrate them as modules into their platform.

The Role of Boundary Resources in governing Platform Innovation

Boundary resources (Ghazawneh and Henfridsson 2013) are a theoretical concept that facilitates our understanding of the governance of the third party innovation of services and applications on the demand side of digital platforms. Boundary resources, which have their theoretical foundation in a synthesis of boundary object theory (Star and Bowker 1999) and the innovation networks literature (Chesbrough et al. 2006), refer to “software tools and regulations that serve as the interface for the arm’s-length relationship between the platform owner and the application developer” (Ghazawneh and Henfridsson 2013, p. 174). In this way they conceptualize two major tasks of a platform owner devolving the innovation of platform services to third party developers. First, they must provide resources to help support third parties develop platform services (Iansiti and Levien 2004), which is effected by technical artefacts such as APIs and SDKs (Ghazawneh and Henfridsson 2013). Second, they must govern third party platform development in order to secure the platform in order to capture value and maintain the integrity of the platform to achieve their platform goals. The governance of platform innovation is frequently effected through contracts (Boudreau and Hagiu 2009). In this way boundary resources incentivize and coordinate distributed third party activities for the innovation of platform services and are essential for the cultivation of an installed base of third party innovators (Ghazawneh and Henfridsson 2013). Whilst boundary resources have been used to understand the governance of platform innovation on the demand side (Huhtamäki et al. 2017), the literature has not employed this approach to examine how third parties can be governed when provisioning modules at scale to a platform authority for the purpose of “coring”, or innovating the platform core.

The key constructs that we use in our analysis are defined summarized in table 1 below.

Construct	Description
Core Architecture	Central part of an innovation platform’s architecture that contains modules of functionality or data from which services and apps can be built.
Peripheral Architecture	Additional platform architecture, separate to the core, where platform complements (apps & services) reside. Complements are built using modules from the core architecture. The governance of the peripheral architecture is separate to the governance of the core.
Platform Authority	Institution(s) having the responsibility and authority to govern the interactions between an ecosystem of actors and an innovation platform, as well as control platform evolution.
Contributors	Actors providing modules of functionality or data to the core architecture of an innovation platform and who are governed by the platform authority in this role. The provision of new modules is essential for the ongoing evolution of an innovation platform’s evolution.
Complementors	Actors using and combining modules of functionality of data from the core architecture to build platform complements, which reside in the peripheral architecture. The interaction of complementors with a platform is governed by the platform authority.
Tools	Artefacts provided by the platform authority which resource and enable ecosystem members to carry out their ecosystem role.
Rules	Artefacts provided by the platform authority which constrain ecosystem members from carrying out actions which may harm a platform and thereby help to secure it.

Table 1. Key constructs used to analyse OGD governance and ecosystem cultivation.

Research Method

We aim to extend boundary resource models of platform governance by identifying the boundary resources which an OGD platform authority uses to govern the supply side innovation of its platform core. We also aim to reveal enabling factors that contribute to the platform authority establishing these boundary resources, as well as how boundary resources interact to facilitate ecosystem cultivation. Our intention is to develop a general understanding (Gregor 2006) and we consequently conduct a qualitative case study (Yin 2003) to infer generalizable insights concerning the emerging phenomenon that we wish to study (Eisenhardt 1989). Based on an information-oriented selection, we chose to study the development and evolution of boundary resources in an OGD platform in Buenos Aires, as it provided rich insights into our research question (Flyvbjerg 2006). The city of Buenos Aires started early on opening up data relative to other cities. It has achieved a certain level of maturity with a reasonable number of datasets being open and services established around them. Our study covers a period of five years, from 2011 to 2015. To mitigate potential sources of bias, we collected multiple sources of evidence: (1) 18 interviews with open data leaders, users and intermediaries; (2) participant observation with government teams from four visits to the field in 2013, 2014 and 2015; (3) archival data comprising documents, legislation, blogs, social media outlets, and previous studies; (4) available data from the open government platform; (5) informal conversations with leaders of the initiative during conferences on open data at regional and international meetings.

Our approach to data analysis is consistent with Eisenhardt’s (1989) approach to building theory from qualitative case study research. We follow an abductive approach to analysis, where concepts from platform architecture and governance are used as sensitizing devices. We coded the data in three overlapping phases, with distinct objectives. Our unit of analysis concerns the interactions between the OGD platform authority and the OGD ecosystem. The first phase of coding of the data aimed to capture the event-time series of platform coring and the emergence of boundary resources; we applied an open coding procedure to classify main concepts, events, actions, decisions, and outcomes. The second phase of coding aimed to consolidate common groups of codes across data sources to generate underlying theoretical concepts. In the third coding phase, we turned to the literature to look for overarching patterns. At this early stage, the outcome of our analysis enabled us to build an initial model. Going forwards, our intention is to develop a comparative case study (Yin 2003) of similar OGD platforms to improve the model's robustness.

Case Analysis

The open data initiative in Buenos Aires has its roots under the tenure of Mauricio Macri who was Mayor of Buenos Aires province from 2007 to 2015 and who aimed to increase the digital presence and use of

digital technology in the city government. The open data initiative launched formally in March 2012, when the government passed the Open Government Decree (156/2012). The Decree put forward the guidelines of a policy based on transparency, collaboration and citizen participation and was a factor enabling the creation of the open data portal (*data.buenosaires.gob.ar*). The Decree also created the *Office of Innovation and Open Government* (hereafter, the Office) within the Ministry of Modernization to lead the implementation of the open data initiative, which served as the platform authority.

The launch of the open data portal in 2012 version released 40 datasets into the platform core, which were sourced from the ministries of transportation, education and culture, among others. The portal was built using CKAN version 1.0, an open source data management application that the team in the Office adapted and customized. The release of these initial data resources in the platform core was possible due to work that the Office started a year earlier to identify and collect digital data sources available in different areas of the government. With the initial datasets identified, the team provided a set of securing rules (ad-hoc guidelines) to help the ministries transform them into machine readable, reusable and open datasets. Later in May 2012, a Ministerial government resolution (190-MMGC/2012) assigned specific powers to the newly created Office to convert those guidelines into formal protocols and procedures that different areas of government should follow to publish their datasets into the open government portal.¹

The Office sourced data for the platform core following a number of steps using tools and rules to facilitate ministries to contribute quality datasets. First, the Office approached ministries that held potentially valuable datasets. These were considered to be data that would best contribute to accountability, citizen interest or the social, economic and cultural development of the city. This was frequently pursued using political channels from within in the government. This approach was accelerated in 2012, through a tool in the form of a data *GovCamp*, a one day event with public servants to introduce them into the new open data initiative and expand the network of potential open data champions across the government. Second, the Office then worked with a given government area to agree on the technical procedures and tools for the construction of the data set, including a pre-defined template that the Office developed as part of their initial activities. Third, rules contained in technical agreements were put in place. In this way a formal annex was signed, which included the format, name of the dataset, the governmental source and responsible area for subsequent updates, among other fields. The technical agreement contained guidelines to encourage the conversion of the data the ministries had available into quality functional datasets. Finally, the process concluded with the integration of the dataset into the core of the platform, and its availability to entrepreneurs and other citizens through interfaces as well as the Buenos Aires Data portal.

The Office also took a number of actions, again using tools and rules, in order to build a community of complementors on the demand side of the Open Government Data Platform. The Office organized a *BA Hackathon* in May 2012 and a two-month contest to develop mobile apps. These initial experiments with resourcing tools established an embryonic community of entrepreneurs who innovated digital services using the datasets in the platform core. In 2013 the Office migrated the platform and the datasets that it contained to CKAN version 2.0. The advantage of version 2.0 was that it provided a superior API through which entrepreneurs could better access datasets in the core platform to innovate with. At the same time the Office sourced an additional 33 datasets, using the process detailed previously, as an act of coring which extended the potential usefulness of the platform. In addition, the Office released and applied rules to the activities of complementors on the demand side. These took the form of general terms and conditions and licensing terms (Creative Commons Argentina 2.5) regarding the use of the datasets through the portal and interfaces in order to govern the use of data accessed from the platform.

During 2013, the city government continued to build the community of complementors on the demand side with tools including further hackathons and apps contests. These events engaged more participants than in 2012 and a larger number of projects emerged. On the supply side the office had largely exhausted its pool of ministries who were amenable to cooperating and contributing datasets. To overcome this difficulty and to encourage other ministries to contribute data, the Office convinced the city authorities to release a new Decree (478/2013), which established that all new data government data produced, stored and/or collected in digital format should be published in open format on the city's open data platform, unless excluded by

¹ In Buenos Aires, each government agency is the final responsible for the publication of datasets while the Office acts as the facilitator/curator of open government data.

specific norms (e.g. personal data laws). The Decree also instructed the Ministries to present an open data plan to the Office by the end of 2014.

Instances of Platform Coring		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2012 - 40 datasets contributed to the core • 2013 – 33 datasets contributed to the core (total of 73 datasets) • 2015 – 95 datasets contributed to the core (total of 168 datasets) 		
Boundary Resources		
	Supply Side - contributing to core	Demand Side - complementing the core
Resourcing	Information Tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Templates to format datasets (2012) Social Tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GovCamp (2012) to socialize open data initiative to public servants 	Software Tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APIs (1 in 2013, 3 in 2015); • Portal (2012 CKAN1.0, 2013 CKAN 2.0) Social Tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hackathons & Competitions (2012-15)
Securing	Contractual Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical Agreements (2012) concerning form of datasets • Data quality guidelines (2012) 	Contractual Rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licenses (2013) Creative Commons Argentina 2.5 • Dataset Use Terms & Conditions (2012)
Enabling Factors		
Organizational forms: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2012 - Office of Innovation and Open Government • 2014 – City Innovation Lab – LabGCBA Open data policies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2012 - Resolution (190-MMGC/2012) formal protocols and procedures for datasets • 2013 - Decree (478/2013) policy mandating all public data to be in open, digital format Broader Open government policies/transparency <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2012 - Open Government Decree (156/2012) 		

Table 2. Instances of Platform Coring, Boundary Resources and Enabling Factors

During 2014 the Office became more sophisticated identifying linkages between the supply side which contributed datasets to the platform core and the demand side which used the datasets of the core platform to produce complements. The Office capitalised on these linkages in to cultivate both the supply side of contributors and the demand side of complementors. This was embodied in the Office’s move to make Hackathons more targeted towards the needs of the ministries. In 2014 the Office launched a Green Hackathon which was targeted at generating complements and uses of open data to help solve the city’s environmental issues. On the one hand this hackathon was aimed at helping to solve issues faced by the ministry of the environment, and on the other hand it was a tool which encouraged the ministry to supply, publish and contribute environmental data to the platform core. At the same time the Office established an innovation lab, called LabGCBA, which brought together a multidisciplinary team comprised of political scientists, journalists, programmers and creatives. The lab provided an environment where teams from the government ministries could go in search of a digital or technical solution to specific problems, which provided further impetus for them to open up and contribute further datasets. An example of this type of engagement came about in 2014 when the Lab worked with the Emergency and Road Safety team, from the ministry of transport, to develop an app that could help identify people at risk of fatality or vulnerability more quickly and effectively. In October 2014, the Office had established itself to the extent that it was able to publish its first Open Data Plan, which consolidated the publication of open data as a public policy for the city government (Gobierno de la Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires 2014b).

By the end of 2015, the Office had worked with government ministries to open up, publish and release a further 95 datasets into the platform core. The Buenos Aires open data platform now contained 168 unique datasets offered in 8 formats. Whilst there were only 22 active mobile apps officially reported on the government website, there had been much citizen interaction with the datasets through the portal and additional apps using the open data were distributed through the major commercial mobile platforms.

We summarise our case analysis in table 2, which illustrates three aspects of our platform coring analysis. First it shows three instances of platform coring of datasets. Second, it illustrates boundary resources which resource (as tools) and secure (as rules) the supply side contributing to platform coring on the one hand,

and the demand side, which uses the data capabilities that platform coring enables for the development of platform complements on the other hand. Third, the table presents enabling factors we identify in our case which facilitate contributions to platform coring as well as the emergence of boundary resources.

Discussion and Outlook

Following our initial analysis we propose a preliminary extended boundary resource model to include the governance of the supply side coring of an OGD platform. We constructed the model building on our case analysis in the following way: by analyzing the boundary resources longitudinally, we were first able to identify whether they fell on the contributing supply side or the complementing demand side of an OGD platform. We were then able to categorize them by type of boundary resource (resourcing or securing). Once we had done this, we were then able to analyze the boundary resources within the case in more depth, and group and cluster them into particular classes—for example the class of informational tools versus social tools as part of resourcing boundary resources on the supply side. Within each class we were able to group the boundary resources we identified yet further into specific examples, such as dataset templates.

Figure 1. Model of Boundary Resources governing Contributions to Platform Coring.

Our tentative model is illustrated in figure 1. The model allows us to analyze interactions between coring events, boundary resources on both sides, and enabling factors which together facilitate the successful establishment of an OGD platform ecosystem. In the center of the model we present the OGD platform architecture, which is abstracted into a platform core containing modules of datasets, and a platform periphery containing apps and services as platform complements. The open interfaces between the platform core and platform periphery, signified by double arrows, enable platform complements to access the dataset modules contained in the platform core. Innovation in the platform core and periphery are governed by the platform authority. On the demand side, the platform authority uses boundary resources, consisting of resourcing tools and securing rules, to govern the innovation of OGD platform complements by complementors as documented by Ghazawneh & Henfridsson 2013. We extend their model to the supply side where the platform authority uses boundary resources, again consisting of resourcing tools and securing rules, to govern the contribution of modules of datasets sourced from a range of government ministries. It does this to enable a process of coring in order to innovate and resource the core architecture of the OGD platform. At the bottom of the model we see enabling factors, typically instituted by the government, in order to facilitate coring events and the establishment and running of boundary resources.

When we apply this model to the case of Buenos Aires, we see that the careful application and balancing of effort on managing boundary resources on both the supply and demand side of the platform gradually led to the cultivation of both sides of the platform ecosystem. This was observed through the platform authority

to sourcing and then coring increasing numbers of datasets from ministries on the contributing supply side, and through increasing engagement of entrepreneurs, acting as complementors, creating platform complements on the demand side. Throughout the evolution of the Buenos Aires' OGD platform a series of enabling factors, instituted by the city government, accelerated the evolution of the ecosystem. These enabling factors took the form of legislation from the government mandating and giving power to the platform authority, as well as obliging ministries to open up and contribute datasets. These factors also lead to institutions which facilitated interactions and symbiosis between complementors and contributors in order that they could meet and match each other's needs. Following on from this point, the application of the model to the case indicates further aspects that led to mutually enhancing interactions between the two sides. For example, the use of resourcing informational tools such as templates and standards maintained in securing contractual rules on the supply side, ensured that quality data sets were provisioned to the platform core. These quality datasets were essential in order to attract and engender trust from developers, entrepreneurs and citizen users, which then facilitated the ignition (Evans & Schmalensee 2016) of the platform. Similarly the use of resourcing boundary resources as social tools in the form of focused theme specific hackathons and competitions not only attracted developers and entrepreneurs on the demand side, but also attracted the attention of particular ministries by increasing the relevance of the OGD platform.

Our intention is to extend our study in order generate a comparative case study using data concerning emergent OGD platforms in other Latin American cities that we are researching, and we believe the resultant analysis will lead to a more robust model. We aim to generate useful empirical and theoretical contributions to key questions regarding OGD platform management and governance (Danneels et al. 2017). In particular, we believe that the concept of boundary resources is fruitful to answer two specific questions of the OGD research agenda: which features and functionalities should be part of the platform on one hand, and what governance decisions should be made to nurture the platform ecosystem on the other. By introducing platform governance terminology we bring greater precision to the understanding of governance of innovation in Open Government Data Platforms (Dawes et al. 2016). In addition, we believe our model has the potential to extend IS theory on the concept of boundary resources (Ghazawneh and Henfridsson 2013) in several ways. First, to extend the application of boundary resources to governing the coring of the supply side (Gawer and Cusumano 2008; Toppenberg et al 2016); so far, existing applications of boundary resources to the governance of platform innovation has largely focused on the demand side (Eaton et al 2015). Second, our model may reveal new classes of boundary resources beyond those identified in previous work. Existing studies (Ghazawneh et al 2013) have typically limited boundary resources, which resource and enable third parties, to software tools such as APIs and SDKs. Our study extends existing work and suggests informational tools such as templates to format the supply of data, and social tools such as hackathons and competitions to enable and encourage the production of platform complements. Finally, our study should complement increasingly dynamic studies of boundary resources (Eaton et al 2015), by suggesting enabling factors which reinforce and support boundary resources, as well as the possibility of mutual reinforcement of boundary resources between the contributing and complementing sides of an innovation platform. We are also optimistic that our model can contribute to practice as it develops and improves. Ultimately, we hope that our model can inform governments at local or national level to design and implement successful OGD platform ecosystems.

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